

PACKING OF DISCONTINUOUS FIBRES

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ABSTRACT

Forced and unforced packing are examined by means of statistical geometry. The maximum unforced packing fraction is modelled by a theory of rigid rods allowing for a distribution in fibre length and orientation. Beyond this limit a constitutive equation for the packing force as a function of volume fraction and fibre orientation distribution is proposed. Based on the results a packing diagram is presented by which the different regimes of packing can be readily identified. The construction of the diagram requires either information about the orientation and dispersion of the fibres or a simple compression experiment.

Keywords: packing, discontinuous fibres, fibre orientation, volume fraction, GMT.

1. INTRODUCTION

A main concern in the formulation of fibre reinforced moulding compounds is to maximise the volume fraction, length-to-diameter ratio, *and* dispersion of the fibres while retaining necessary melt flow properties. Therefore an understanding of the mechanisms which govern and limit fibre packing is essential.

Some insight can be gained by analysing the packing of rigid rods. This predicts a maximum packing fraction as a function of the fibre aspect ratio. Evans and Gibson [1] performed such an analysis for 3-D random fibre orientation. Presently we have generalised their result to account for an arbitrary fibre orientation distribution.

The rigid-rod theory alone is sufficient only at aspect ratios below, say, 50 (typically short-fibre injection moulding compounds). At higher aspect ratios the fibres are more flexible and permit forced packing far beyond the rigid-rod limit. Thus in this regime one needs a constitutive theory relating the volume fraction to the force per unit area exerted by the fibre network. Such theories have been proposed for certain special cases of fibre orientation [2-4]; here we present one that allows for any planar orientation distribution except a highly aligned one.

Figure 1: Packing regimes

2. PACKING REGIMES

Figure 1 schematically defines different packing regimes in terms of fibre volume fraction (ϕ) and aspect ratio ($r=l/d$). In the unforced-packing regime no packing forces act between the fibres or on boundaries. In the forced-packing regime the fibres must bend between contact points and exert elastic forces on each other and on any boundaries. The borderline between the forced and unforced regimes is defined by the maximum unforced packing fraction ϕ_0 . For low and intermediate aspect ratios, say up to 500 for glass fibres, ϕ_0 is approximately the maximum packing of rigid rods; for very large aspect ratios, however, the fibres may not be straight even when unloaded and rigid-rod theory will underestimate ϕ_0 .

At high enough volume fractions the packing forces will cause fibre fracture. However, there is no sharp transition into this fracture regime since there will be a gradually increasing number of fibre fractures with increased packing.

3. GEOMETRICAL CONCEPTS

The present theory assumes that the fibre suspension is statistically homogeneous and that the fibres are spatially well dispersed. The latter essentially implies that the spatial and orientational distributions of fibres are independent, thus excluding the case of a mat consisting of fibre bundles. The fibre diameter is taken to be uniform.

Small deviations from perfect fibre dispersion (local order) can be accounted for by replacing each fibre by a group of parallel fibres. We thus introduce the *dispersion function* ξ , which is the reciprocal of the number of fibres in a representative group. Thus $0 \leq \xi \leq 1$ and at perfect dispersion $\xi=1$.

The average number N_i of fibre centrelines intersecting an average test fibre is [4]

$$\bar{N}_i = n\bar{l}^2df + \frac{1}{4}\pi n\bar{l}d^2(g+1), \quad (1)$$

where n is the number fraction of fibres, \bar{l} is the number-average fibre length, and f and g are functions of the fibre orientation distribution.

The average number of fibre-fibre *contacts* N_c along an average fibre is obtained by replacing d by $2d$ in Equation 1; thus, in terms of volume fraction,

$$\bar{N}_c = 4\phi\left(\frac{2}{\pi}\bar{r}f + g + 1\right), \quad (2)$$

where $\bar{r}=\bar{l}/d$ is the number-average fibre aspect ratio. The orientation functions are [4]

$$f = \oint\oint |\sin(\theta' - \theta)| \psi(\theta')\psi(\theta) d\theta' d\theta, \quad (3)$$

$$g = \oint\oint |\cos(\theta' - \theta)| \psi(\theta')\psi(\theta) d\theta' d\theta, \quad (4)$$

where $\psi(\theta)$ is the in-plane fibre orientation distribution function.

4. UNFORCED PACKING

One obtains directly from Equation 2

$$\phi_0 = \frac{\bar{N}_0/4}{\frac{2}{\pi}\bar{r}f + g + 1}, \quad (5)$$

thus relating the unforced volume fraction ϕ_0 directly to the maximum average number of contact points per fibre \bar{N}_0 for straight fibres. Now the key assumption will be made that maximum unforced packing occurs when each fibre is supported by a fixed number of fibre groups. Thus $\bar{N}_0\xi$ is a constant which is independent of fibre aspect ratio and orientation distribution. This being a slender-body theory it should predict $\phi_0=1/\xi$ at $\bar{r}=1$. This gives $\bar{N}_0=8/\xi$ and we obtain

$$\phi_0 = \frac{2/\xi}{\frac{2}{\pi}\bar{r}f + g + 1}. \quad (6)$$

At large aspect ratios, $\bar{r} \gg 1$, this reduces to

$$\phi_0 = \frac{\pi}{\bar{r}\xi f}. \quad (7)$$

In the special case of 3-D random orientation, $f=\pi/4$, perfect dispersion, $\xi=1$, and uniform aspect ratio, $\bar{r}=r$, this formula reduces to the result obtained by Evans and Gibson [1],

$$\phi_0 = 4/r. \quad (8)$$

For very large aspect ratios, the fibres bend significantly already under self-loading, e.g. gravity and surface related forces, and \bar{N}_0 as measured on a fibre bed resting on a horizontal surface must be higher than predicted by any rigid-rod theory. This \bar{N}_0 , however, is more difficult to predict since it depends on the type of microforces acting within the fibre bed, the thickness of the fibre bed, etc.

If the aspect ratio is sufficiently large the average unforced aspect ratio between contact points \bar{r}_0 (rather than \bar{N}_0) should be constant. Thus (7) is replaced by

$$\phi_0 = \frac{\pi}{8\bar{r}_0\xi f}. \quad (9)$$

5. FORCED PACKING

In this section we derive the packing force per unit area $P(\phi)$ in the forced packing regime. This analysis is restricted to planar fibre beds and large fibre aspect ratios, $\bar{r} \gg 1$.

Each fibre makes contact with a number of other fibres crossing above and below. When the volume fraction is increased above the maximum unforced packing limit the fibres act as beams supported at the contact points. Each contact between two fibres, or groups of parallel fibres, is taken to correspond to a beam segment and is called a *node*. A node is characterized by the length of the beam segment, taken as the node spacing a , the contact force p , the deflection δ , and the compliance $s = d\delta/dp$.

We will assume that on an incremental increase of ϕ , the increase in packing force is evenly distributed among the existing nodes, i.e., dp is uniform. This allows us to write the average incremental node deflection in terms of the average nodal compliance:

$$\overline{d\delta} = \bar{s} dp. \quad (10)$$

An elastic potential energy function can now be defined

$$d\mathcal{W} = \eta p \overline{d\delta} = \eta \frac{\overline{ps}}{\bar{s}} \overline{d\delta}, \quad (11)$$

where η is the number of nodes per unit volume. Under the assumption that $\bar{\delta} \ll d$ one can show that

$$\overline{d\delta} = \frac{d}{\phi} d\phi. \quad (12)$$

Now, by substitution of (12) into (11), we have

$$d\mathcal{W} = \eta \frac{\overline{ps}}{\bar{s}} \frac{d}{\phi} d\phi. \quad (13)$$

Differentiation of the potential energy function gives the packing pressure:

$$P = \frac{d\mathcal{W}}{d\phi} \phi = d \cdot \eta \frac{\overline{ps}}{\bar{s}}. \quad (14)$$

Again differentiating with respect to p and integrating with respect to ϕ ,

$$P = d^2 \int_0^\phi \frac{\eta}{\bar{s}\phi} d\phi. \quad (15)$$

Using the dispersion function ξ , we have $\eta = 4\xi\phi/(\pi d^2 \bar{a})$ and obtain the result

$$P = \frac{4}{\pi} \xi \int_0^\phi \frac{d\phi}{\bar{a}\bar{s}}. \quad (16)$$

It remains to find appropriate forms of the functions $\bar{a}(\phi)$ and $\bar{s}(\phi)$.

The average node spacing is obtained from Equation 2 as

$$\bar{a} = 2 \frac{\bar{l}}{\xi N_c} = \frac{\pi}{4} \frac{d}{\xi f \phi}, \quad (17)$$

where only the first term of (2) has been used since $\bar{r} \gg 1$.

The node compliance is modelled by a centrally loaded cylindrical beam with a no-rotation end condition:

$$\bar{s} = \frac{\bar{a}^3 \xi}{3\pi E d^4}, \quad (18)$$

where E is the Young's modulus of the fibre.

Substituting Equations 17 and 18 into (16) and integrating, we arrive at

$$P = 6.3E(\xi f)^4 \phi^5. \quad (19)$$

6. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE AND RESULTS

A Glass Mat reinforced Thermoplastic (GMT) sheet for compression moulding was examined. This material (Azdel, Inc.) has a matrix of polypropylene and is produced by a slurry deposition process which disperses the fibres so that ξ is of the order of 1. This is in contrast with melt impregnated grades in which the chopped fibres are present as bundles of several hundred parallel fibres. The fibre arrangement in this material is almost perfectly planar, and the fibre aspect ratio is close to uniform, $\bar{r} \approx 1000$.

The in-plane fibre orientation distribution was measured by image analysis of polished sections. This technique has been described in detail elsewhere [6]. The sheet was cut into square samples of $130 \times 130 \text{ mm}^2$, and the matrix removed by pyrolysis at 560°C for 1 hour. The unforced packing fraction was determined from the weight and thickness of the resulting fibre bed. To study the forced-packing regime we used a squeeze-flow rheometer with 110 mm-diameter parallel plates. The fibre bed was compressed between the plates at a rate of 1 mm/s while compressive force and displacement were recorded.

The orientation function, calculated from the image analysis results according to Equation 3, was $f=0.46$. The fibre weight per unit area of the ashed sheet was 473 g/m^2 , and the unloaded volume fraction was $\phi_0=0.023$.

7. DISCUSSION

Equations 7, 9, and 19 together make up the packing diagram in Figure 2. Line (a) is the packing pressure-volume fraction curve described by Equation 19. The slope of the curve is thus prescribed to the value 5, and its exact position is determined by ξf . Line (a) is supported by our experiment in that the experimental data have the theoretical slope of 5 in this region. Lines (b) and (c) represent the maximum unforced packing for very slender fibres; thus Line (b) as shown is asymptotic and will shift to the right for aspect ratios below about 300. Line (d) represents the maximum unforced packing of slender fibres, Equation 9, and is therefore valid only well above its intersection with (e). It is a function of orientation and dispersion through ξf . The only support for Line (d) at present is the experimental support for Equation 8 found in the literature [1]. Line (e) represents the limit of packing of monodisperse spheres, $\phi_0 \approx 0.7$; it is therefore independent of orientation and dispersion. The entire packing diagram is thus defined by two parameters: ξf and \bar{r}_0 .

The value of ξf for the examined fibre bed is 0.46, using the measured value $f=0.46$ and assuming perfect dispersion ($\xi=1$). The aspect ratio, $\bar{r}=1000$, is assumed to lie beyond the limit for rigid-rod theory ($\bar{r} > 8\bar{r}_0$). Thus ϕ_0 is independent of \bar{r} , and Equation 9 gives $\bar{r}_0=55$. Figure 2 was consequently plotted for $\xi f=0.46$ and $\bar{r}_0=55$. Any decrease in ξf (decrease in dispersion or increase in alignment) shifts the Lines (a) and (d) towards the right.

Since the orientation and dispersion functions f and ξ always enter as the product ξf , an orientation measurement is not necessary to plot the diagram. Instead the diagram can be determined by a single experiment: Lines (a) and (b) can be fitted to the $P-\phi$ curve, giving ξf and \bar{r}_0 , respectively. With the present data (circles) this alternative procedure would give $\xi f \approx 0.40$ (as compared to 0.46).

Each line in Figure 2 describes a single mechanism; in practice, the transitions between the governing mechanisms will involve combinations of mechanisms, smoothing the curves (as in Figure 1). Moreover, the curve for the packing pressure, Line (a), is valid for a fibre network in the absence of resin. The liquid resin present during processing will lubricate the fibre network and partly relax the packing pressure. Therefore the packing pressure predicted by this theory should be regarded as an upper bound.

Figure 2: Packing diagram for a planar fibre bed with $\xi f=0.46$ and $\bar{r}_0=55$.

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